

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

HYDROPONIC FODDER PRODUCTION IN OIL-CONTAMINATED AREAS OF THE ABSHERON PENINSULA

Bagirov H.,

PhD on ag.sc., doc. Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry of ANAS,

Babanli M.,

doctor on agr. sc., prof.

Mammadov U.

PhD on ag.sc., doc. Institute of Catalysis Chemistry of ANAS

Abstract

The Absheron peninsula is one of the economically developed areas of our republic, as the region of the ancient oil and gas industry, disturbed and polluted lands are widespread here. In the Absheron economic district, which produces 60.5% of the republic's industrial output, degraded and polluted lands as a result of man-made processes are widespread. Cleanup of oil-contaminated areas in our country and effective use of those lands, cultivation of green fodder in a soilless environment and reduction of irrigation water use during ripening can be considered as the beginning of the economy not only of today but also of the future.

Keywords: soil, ecology, hydroponic feed, relief, hydrographic network.

Introduction. Absheron peninsula differs from other regions of the republic due to its ecological conditions. The total area of the peninsula is 213 thousand ha, its length from west to east is 60 km, and its width is 30 km at its widest point. The surface of the territory consists of wide plains, flat depressions, hills and plateaus. While the western part of the peninsula is relatively high, the eastern part (along the coast of the Caspian Sea) is 26 meters below sea level. Such diversity is also evident in its geological structure. It was determined that sediments belonging to the Tertiary and Quaternary periods were formed in the area. Cretaceous period sediments are found in the north-western part. The climate is dry subtropical, the average monthly air temperature is 3-4°C, and in July it is 24-26°C. The amount of annual precipitation is 195 mm (Baku observatory) and 245 mm (Mashtaga). The average monthly air temperature in this area is 5.4-14.6°C during the growing season, and the low rainfall slows down the formation of vegetation. Semi-xerophytic and semi-holophytic plants have formed here mainly semi-desert ephemerals: wormwood, sedum, blackberry (in saline areas), winter grass, salt broom, etc. The soils of the area were formed as a result of the interaction of the above-mentioned natural factors. The deflation process occurring in the sands of the Agcagil Absheron sedimentary rocks and the new Caspian terraces has a special role in the modern formation of the Absheron relief. The central part of the peninsula has a more complex relief. Along with deflation, the denudation process is observed here. The central part of the peninsula has a more complex topography. Along with deflation, the denudation process is observed here. Water erosion activity can also be noted in the central part of the peninsula. The lithological composition of the rocks has a special importance in the formation of the relief of the Absheron peninsula. Sands and gravels are more prone to deflation. In Absheron, the blowing of saline clays is also widely formed [1,2].

According to its morphological structure, the Absheron peninsula valley forms the southeastern end of

the Greater Caucasus. Neotectonic movements of different amplitudes are observed here. Due to this, tectonic relief is formed. Conical hills of different sizes and shapes exist on the peninsula as a result of the activity of mud volcanoes. In the south-western part of Absheron, an inversion (inclined) relief has developed. Here, the relief consists of monoclinical elevations and synginal plateaus consisting of Absheron limestones resistant to denudation. Most of the Absheron peninsula has a smooth and poorly broken relief.

Absheron is a complex geological complex consisting mainly of paleogene, neogene and quaternary period sediments, its thickness is 8000-9000 m. The sediments represented by sand, sandy loam, siltstone and clay are more widely formed. These rocks make up almost half of the total thickness (up to 3400 m) in the paleogene-neogene section and create a very complex system of layers. Two levels are noticeable in the geological structure of the peninsula: lower - paleogene - miocene and upper - pliocene - pleistocene. The lower level is located at a considerable depth, connecting the Absheron peninsula with the south-eastern Caucasus.

Grey-brown and their saline, irrigated saline, marshy, advanced and primitive grey-brown types were mainly formed in the Absheron peninsula. In Absheron region, which has a total area of 79,000 hectares, 38,000 hectares are cultivated, 4,364 hectares are perennial crops, including 1,664 hectares are vineyards, 3,165 hectares are subtropical plants (almonds, olives, figs, etc.) and the rest are under pasture [3].

Absheron peninsula is a complex and difficult research object due to soil and climate conditions. Such complexity is explained not by the presence of man-made disturbed land areas on the peninsula, but by the poor development of the soil layer by nature, as well as by the complex climatic conditions, especially in the area, the rainfall is low and there are many windy days. Average absolute maximum air temperature in the peninsula is 40-42°C annually. The average absolute minimum varies from location to location, ranging from -7-10°C, and the multi-year average temperature is 13.5-

14.6°C. The climate of the main part of the Absheron peninsula belongs to the climate type of temperate-hot semi-desert and dry steppes with dry summers. Its geographical position and physical-geographical conditions play an important role in the formation of the modern climate of the area. Thus, the area is surrounded by the Caspian Sea, and on the west side by the south-eastern end of the great Caucasus range, it has a strong influence on the climate. Summer is dry and hot. In winter, the weather is often cloudy, it often rains.

Absheron peninsula is considered one of the driest areas of Azerbaijan. Therefore, the hydrographic network of the area consists of several small rivers and lakes. According to the authors who conducted hydrological researches in Absheron, rivers can be divided into two groups according to their flow regime: Dry rivers: their flow is fed by heavy rains, snow water and partly by underground water. Temporary rivers are formed due to heavy rains. Most of the rivers dry up in summer. Sumgaitchay and Ceyrankechmez rivers flow on average 100-150 days a year, and the rest of the months are dry for most of the year. The maximum water consumption of rivers is observed in the season of spring-autumn rains, and the minimum is observed in the dry season - summer season. The water balance of lakes (Masazir, Boyukshor, Ganli gol, etc.) and its elements depend on human economic activity and atmospheric sediments. Atmospheric sediments, underground waters, and industrial-domestic waters discharged into lakes constitute the main food source of the lakes [4,5]. On the peninsula, fairly sweet and slightly mineralized groundwater is used. Groundwater depends on the chemical composition of the rocks in which it collects. The natural regime of underground water changes according to the seasons of the year.

Analysis of results. Hydroponic fodder is considered one of the most profitable promising areas in the development of agriculture in the advanced countries of the world. In order to meet the demand for green fodder related to the development of livestock and poultry

farms in large cities and villages, the creation of a permanent fodder base is one of the priority issues. In the era of globalization of the world, the reduction of land use areas and the annual decrease in productivity once again make it actual to bring up the development prospects of alternative fodder farms in the future and to implement the works on application. In this regard, the installation of hydroponic facilities and the availability of green, high-quality feed throughout the year play an important role in the prevention of global food security, which has become a reality today. The main property of hydroponic fodder production is related to the ease of application of this field and the ability to deliver the fodder to the demand centers on time. Barley is a cereal grain used as a final feed for livestock in the United States and Canada. These sprouts are high in protein and fiber and have a natural balance of protein, fat and energy. Compared to corn, barley feed has 95% higher energy content and better digestibility. Barley meal is one of the most nutritious sprouts and is rich in important nutrients, vitamins and minerals. Using of barley feed will improve the general health and welfare of large breeds of small cattle. Using of barley feed provides the following benefits for livestock:

- Reduces the frequency of digestive disorders such as abdominal pain and bloating;
- Stimulates the immune system;
- Important nutritional values are in natural balance;
- High fiber, energy and protein levels;
- Rich in enzymes;
- Low acid content;
- High digestibility. No aflatoxin. The rate of aflatoxin increases when stored in silage. It has been scientifically proven to increase the quality and productivity of meat and milk in animals. The reproductive capacity of animals increases according to the A-E biotin and folic acid vitamins and natural enzymes. It is known that the proportion of crude protein in the total ration of 15% or more has a positive effect on milk yield and milk fat ratio.

Test results

The name of the test	Unit of measurement	The name of the technical normative document taken as the basis for the product	Applied examination (test) methods	Test result	Normative standard requirement	Measurement uncertainty	Evaluation of test results (quarantine status)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
SAMPLE 0001: FODDER/ Fodder (hydroponic energetic)							
*Determination of starch	%	-	QOST 1084598	43.5	-		Factual
*Fat determination	%	-	QOST 13496.15-2016	1.01	-		Factual
Energetic value, 100 gr	kcal	-	By calculation method	203.75	-		Factual
*Determination of wet cellulose	%	-	QOST 13496.2-91	1.5	-		Factual
*Protein determination	%	-	QOST 13496.4-93	6.24	-		Factual
*Determination of ash	%	-	QOST 13979.6-69	1.9	-		Factual

Figure 1. Laboratory analysis indicators of hydroponic feed

Barley should be kept in large tanks in clean water, without any mineral and organic fertilizers, changing the water 3-4 times a day. This process takes 30 hours. After 30 hours, soaked barley is kept in a corner of the room in the dark for 20 hours. After 20 hours, it is placed on the shelves in another bright part of the room. Within 5-7 days, the formation of sprouts approximately 2-4 cm high is observed. Within 10 days, 10-12 cm growth is observed. Fully ripe feed is wrapped from the tray and given to the animal by mixing 2-3 kg of dry hay or grass for every 10 kg of feed. It is necessary to supply approximately 400-600 kg of fodder for each animal (for 1 month). It should be taken into account

that the animal eats 20-25 kg of feed per day. It is planned to give the fodder to 2 heads of large horned animals, 4 heads of domestic pigs, 10-15 heads of small horned animals, as well as 40-50 heads of domestic rabbits and 150-200 live birds. Forage is more useful than dry grass and hay. Its usefulness is measured by the amount of protein it contains. Protein is considered the main nutrient in animal nutrition. As a result of feeding with more protein feed, there is a significant difference in both the quantity of meat and the quality of milk. This is a response to the excessive demand for agricultural goods.

Figure 2. Hydroponic fodder production in an oil-contaminated area

The result. 1. There is no need to use land; 2. Using modern technological methods, the water supplied to the plant is saved; 3. Buying a healthy ecological product using clean substrate and water; 4. Achieving a high productivity indicator in the same place; 5. Prevention of environmental pollution.

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